

Survey MT use, revising, being revised

Start of Block: Information et consentement

Welcome!

This questionnaire accompanies the study “Quality Assurance in the Age of Neural Machine Translation: Practices and Perceptions of Revision and Post-editing”.

The goal of the study is to improve our knowledge of revision and translation using machine translation (MT). More specifically, it aims to provide an overview of revision and translation practices, and to measure phenomena such as the difficulty of revision and post-editing activities. The study is taking place in several countries (including Switzerland, Belgium and Canada), and is intended for translation professionals who use MT, revise and/or are revised.

This research is funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and conducted by:

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Isabelle Robert, professor, University of Antwerp, Belgium

You will need between 15 and 20 minutes to fill out this questionnaire, depending on the number of activities that apply to you (using MT, revising, being revised).

The survey will be available **until [specific date]**.

It is available in [different languages depending on context: French, English, Italian and/or Dutch] (you can change the language at any time from the drop-down menu in the top right-hand corner).

For any questions or queries, you can email us at: aurelien.riondel@uantwerpen.be or isabelle.robert@uantwerpen.be

Page Break

Before we start, we need to be sure that you consent to take part in this study.

Here are some information about how your data will be managed:

Your answers to the survey will be collected completely anonymously. We have no way of linking your answers to you. We will not record any personal data that can identify you.

Since the survey is completely anonymous, we will not be able to follow up on your participation or destroy your answers once they have been submitted. If you want to withdraw while taking part in the survey, simply type “I withdraw” in any free text box.

The data will be safely stored and archived on a server. **The researchers of this study have the right to share anonymous databases** (in which participants are not recognizable to anyone) **with (inter)national colleagues** in the context of (this and/or later) scientific research. These data files are not accessible to other parties, including yourself or companies/organizations that do not fit within scientific research institutions.

You can leave the questionnaire at any time, and this will not entail any disadvantage or loss of benefits. This study was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee for the Social Sciences and Humanities of the University of Antwerp. The researchers confirm that provided information accurately describes the project.

I have read and understood the information about the study

I voluntarily agree to participate

Page Break

Thank you very much for participating in this survey, we really appreciate it! To speed up the process, you can use the arrows on your keyboard to select your answer and the 'tab' key to move on to the next line or question.

End of Block: Information et consentement

Start of Block: Définitions et questions de sélection/préliminaires

In this survey, we define the following terms as follows:

MT-assisted translation: producing a translated text using machine translation (MT). The term includes post-editing in the traditional sense and the intermittent use of machine translation, i.e. alternating between editing the machine output and traditional translation (see below).

Traditional translation: translating a text without using machine translation. This includes translating in a CAT-tool (Trados Studio, MemoQ, Transit...) and using the traditional functions of such software like translation memories and terminology databases.

Revision: checking a translation produced by a person, who may or may not have used machine translation. Only written revision is considered here (oral revision in pairs is not taken into account)

Do you translate using machine translation (MT-assisted translation)?

Yes

No

For how long have you been doing MT-assisted translation? (in years)

▼ 0 ... 40 years or more

How often do you do MT-assisted translation?

- Every day or almost every day
 - Once or several times a week
 - Once or several times a month
 - Once or several times a year
 - Less than once a year
-

Have you received specific training in machine translation or post-editing?

- Yes
 - No
-

Could you briefly describe the training?

Do you revise?

Yes

No

For how long have you been revising? (in years)

▼ 0 ... 40 years or more

How often do you revise?

- Every day or almost every day
 - Once or several times a week
 - Once or several times a month
 - Once or several times a year
 - Less than once a year
-

Have you received specific training in revision?

- Yes
 - No
-

Could you briefly describe the training?

Are you revised (systematically, regularly or occasionally)?

Yes

No

For how long have you been revised? (in years)

▼ 0 ... 40 years or more

How often are you revised?

- Every day or almost every day
- Once or several times a week
- Once or several times a month
- Once or several times a year
- Less than once a year

End of Block: Définitions et questions de sélection/préliminaires

Start of Block: Bloc traduction à l'aide de la TA / post-édition

This section is about MT-assisted translation. Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *When I am doing MT-assisted translation...*

	Never	Almost never	Sometimes	Often	Almost always	Always	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
I rework a text that has been fully translated by machine translation (post-editing in the traditional sense)	<input type="radio"/>						
I use machine translation intermittently (for each segment, I choose whether to use machine translation or not)	<input type="radio"/>						
I only use machine translation as a source of inspiration (I do not rework the machine output, but translate from scratch and might copy/paste some wording from the machine translation)	<input type="radio"/>						
I focus on the translated text and only consult the source text occasionally (monolingual post-editing)	<input type="radio"/>						
I carry out a comparative re-reading, taking a piece of the source text as a starting point	<input type="radio"/>						
I carry out comparative re-reading taking a piece of the target text as a starting point	<input type="radio"/>						
I use paper (printed source text, printout of the post-edited translation for review, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>						

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *When I am doing MT-assisted translation...*

	Never	Almost never	Sometimes	Often	Almost always	Always	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
I change the translation if I think it 'sounds better' after modification	<input type="radio"/>						
I spend time improving things that are correct but not optimal	<input type="radio"/>						
I ask myself how I can justify a change before editing the translation	<input type="radio"/>						
I compare the machine output with my own translation	<input type="radio"/>						
I modify machine suggestions that are perfectly correct and adequate	<input type="radio"/>						
I spend more time editing the machine output than translating the particular piece from scratch	<input type="radio"/>						
I take a few seconds to decide whether to rework the machine's suggestion or re-translate a segment from scratch	<input type="radio"/>						
I reuse as many elements of the machine output as possible	<input type="radio"/>						
I am influenced by the machine's suggestions and cannot come up with my own translation solutions (I feel hypnotised by the machine's suggestions)	<input type="radio"/>						

I feel stressed

I laugh or smile when I read the machine translation suggestion

I say to myself 'that's a good one' when I see a suggestion from the machine

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *translation...*

Compared to traditional translation, when I am doing MT-assisted

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
I feel less creative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am more tired	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel a greater need to be re-read by someone else	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I go faster	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I appreciate typing less	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find it easier to come up with good wording, because the machine suggestions serve as a source of inspiration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *In general, when I am doing MT-assisted translation...*

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
I discover translation solutions in the suggestions made by the machine that I would not have thought of myself	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I ask myself questions that I would not have asked otherwise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I think about the standards I apply in my job (grammar rules, translation standards, terminology conventions, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How difficult are the following tasks when you are doing MT-assisted translation?

	Very easy	Easy	Somewhat easy	Neither easy nor difficult	Somewhat difficult	Difficult	Very difficult	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
Identifying problems in the machine translation output	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When faced with a translation solution that has caught your attention, deciding whether to change the translation or leave the text as is	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Once you have identified a problem, finding a way of solving it (without adding another problem)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Maintaining a high level of attention over an extended period of time (more than 30 minutes)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Taking advantage of the suggestions made by machine translation and not re-translating everything yourself	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Bloc traduction à l'aide de la TA / post-édition

Start of Block: Bloc révision

This section is about revision. Choose the option that best corresponds to your professional life.

	Never	Almost never	Sometimes	Often	Almost always	Always	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
I revise the translation and hand over the finalised text (sending the text to the customer, project manager, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>						
I revise the translation and send it back to the translator, who finalises it	<input type="radio"/>						
I revise colleagues of a lower hierarchical rank	<input type="radio"/>						
I revise colleagues of a higher hierarchical rank	<input type="radio"/>						
I revise people I know little or nothing about (e.g. people from outside the department)	<input type="radio"/>						

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *When I am revising...*

	Never	Almost never	Sometimes	Often	Almost always	Always	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
I focus on the translated version and only consult the source text occasionally (monolingual revision)	<input type="radio"/>						
I carry out a comparative re-reading, taking a piece of the source text as a starting point	<input type="radio"/>						
I carry out a comparative re-reading, taking a piece of the target text as a starting point	<input type="radio"/>						
I work in a CAT-tool, e.g. Trados Studio, MemoQ, Transit	<input type="radio"/>						
I work in a word processor, e.g. Microsoft Word	<input type="radio"/>						
I use paper (e.g. printed source text, printed text to be revised)	<input type="radio"/>						
I read the translation to be revised aloud to myself	<input type="radio"/>						

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *When I am revising...*

	Never	Almost never	Sometimes	Often	Almost always	Always	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
I feel stressed	<input type="radio"/>						
I get angry with the translator	<input type="radio"/>						
I feel like I am doing the work of the translator for them	<input type="radio"/>						
I worry that I might do something wrong (damage the text, offend the translator, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>						
I feel uncomfortable about intervening in someone else's work	<input type="radio"/>						
I laugh or smile when I read the translator's suggestion	<input type="radio"/>						
I feel a sense of pride (e.g. because I have managed to carry out a complex task)	<input type="radio"/>						
I say to myself 'that's a good one' when I see a translation choice	<input type="radio"/>						
I appreciate the challenge of the task	<input type="radio"/>						
I feel satisfied (e.g. that I have improved the text, that I have contributed to the improvement of the translator)	<input type="radio"/>						

I change the translation if I think it 'sounds better' after modification

I spend time improving things that are correct but not optimal

I compare the draft translation with my own translation

I ask myself how I can justify a change before editing the translation

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *When I am revising...*

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
I discover translation solutions in the draft translation that I would not have thought of myself	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I ask myself questions that I would not have asked otherwise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I think about the standards I apply in my job (grammar rules, translation standards, terminology conventions, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I respect the stylistic choices made by the translator.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I accept approaches to translation that are different from my own (e.g. more or less literal strategies)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
Revising requires me to make an unpleasant cognitive effort	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Revising takes up a lot of my time	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Revising helps me diversify my daily work (and not only to translate)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Revising helps me satisfy my intellectual curiosity by giving me exposure to more subjects than if I were just translating	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How difficult are the following tasks when you are revising?

	Very easy	Easy	Somewhat easy	Neither easy nor difficult	Somewhat difficult	Difficult	Very difficult	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
Identifying problems in the translation being revised	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When faced with a translation solution that has caught your attention, deciding whether to change the translation or leave the text as is	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Once you have identified a problem, finding a way of solving it (without adding another problem)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Maintaining a high level of attention over an extended period of time (more than 30 minutes)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Explaining the reasons for the changes you made	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Only making the changes that are necessary (not making superfluous changes)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *When I am revising...*

	Never	Almost never	Sometimes	Often	Almost always	Always	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
I use comments to explain some of my edits	<input type="radio"/>						
I explain my work in a conversation with the translator	<input type="radio"/>						
I provide written feedback (other than an evaluation sheet, e.g. comments in an email)	<input type="radio"/>						
I fill in an evaluation sheet	<input type="radio"/>						
I receive comments on translation choices from the translator	<input type="radio"/>						

To avoid any misunderstanding of the following question, here is a definition: **Interactions around revision:** any communication induced by revision. Communication may be written or oral, take place before or after the revision, and have different aims (giving an explanation, asking a question, making an assessment, etc.).

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *When I revise...*

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
interactions around revision allow me to have stimulating professional discussions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
interactions around revision allow me to break away from the loneliness of translation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
interactions around revision allow me to strengthen my relationships with my colleagues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
interactions around revision take up a lot of time	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I dread interactions around revision	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Choose the option that corresponds to your experience. *I had a conflict relating to revision when I was revising someone else's work*

- During the last 7 days
- During the last 30 days
- During the last 365 days
- More than a year ago
- Never
- Not applicable or prefer not to answer

End of Block: Bloc révision

Start of Block: Bloc être révisé·e

This section is about being revised. Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience

	Never	Almost never	Sometimes	Often	Almost always	Always	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
When I have been revised, I feel offended	<input type="radio"/>						
When I have been revised, I feel discouraged	<input type="radio"/>						
When I have been revised, I get angry	<input type="radio"/>						
When I have been revised and the changes are significant , I question my ability to translate	<input type="radio"/>						
When I am revised, I feel a sense of security	<input type="radio"/>						
When I am revised, I feel satisfied that my work is validated by another professional	<input type="radio"/>						
When I have been revised and the changes are minor , I feel a sense of pride	<input type="radio"/>						
When I have been revised and the changes are minor , I feel happy	<input type="radio"/>						

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
When I am revised, I deepen my knowledge of the rules to be followed (e.g. grammar rules of the target language)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When I am revised, I discover translation solutions that I would not have thought of myself	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When I am revised, I am able to analyse the changes made to my texts (e.g. determining the seriousness of an error, distinguishing whether a change is necessary or contingent)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Being revised allows me to progress in translation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Being revised requires me to work on myself (e.g. to accept being revised)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Being revised requires a lot of my time (e.g. to consult or finalise the revised text)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Being revised requires me to make an effort to comment on my translation or to pass on information in another way	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Being revised allows me to be more creative when translating	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Being revised allows me to take more risks when translating	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Being revised allows me to translate more quickly (for example, by foregoing a – final – proofreading)

○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *When I am revised...*

	Never	Almost never	Sometimes	Often	Almost always	Always	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
prior to revision, I comment on translation choices (sources, explanation, justification, etc.)	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
I receive comments in the margins of the translation	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
I receive an evaluation sheet	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
I receive oral feedback	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
I receive written feedback (other than an evaluation sheet, e.g. comments in an email)	○	○	○	○	○	○	○

In case you did not see it earlier in the survey, here is a definition: **Interactions around revision:** any communication induced by revision. Communication may be written or oral, take place before or after the revision, and have different aims (giving an explanation, asking a question, making an assessment, etc.).

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *When I am revised...*

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
interactions around revision allow me to have stimulating professional discussions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
interactions around revision allow me to break away from the loneliness of translation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
interactions around revision allow me to strengthen my relationships with my colleagues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
interactions around revision take up a lot of time	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I dread interactions around revision	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
interactions around revision increase feelings of resentment (vexation, frustration, anger, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
interactions around revision improve the way I experience revision	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Choose the option that corresponds to your experience. *I had a conflict relating to revision of my translation work*

- During the last 7 days
- During the last 30 days
- During the last 365 days
- More than a year ago
- Never
- Not applicable or prefer not to answer

End of Block: Bloc être révisé·e

Start of Block: Bloc évolution et appréciation des activités

Thank you for filling in the survey so far! You have now completed most of the survey. There are two screens left, shorter than the previous ones

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *Compared to when I started doing MT-assisted translation...*

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
I get more out of machine translation (e.g. I make fewer changes to machine translation suggestions)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I can spot and correct typical machine translation errors more easily	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find the task easier in general	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *Compared to when I started revising...*

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
I make fewer changes to translations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I can explain my changes better	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find the task easier in general	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Choose the option that best corresponds to your experience. *Compared to when I received my first revisions...*

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable or prefer not to answer
I am more accepting of having my work revised	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have greater emotional distance with my revised work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am better at analysing the changes made to my texts (e.g. determining the seriousness of an error, distinguishing whether a change is necessary or contingent)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How much do you like **doing MT-assisted translation**?

- I do not like it at all 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- I like it very much 7
- Not applicable or prefer not to answer

How much do you like **revising**?

- I do not like it at all 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- I like it very much 7
- Not applicable or prefer not to answer

How much do you like **being revised**?

- I do not like it at all 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- I like it very much 7
- Not applicable or prefer not to answer

How much do you like **translating the traditional way**?

- I do not like it at all 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- I like it very much 7
- Not applicable or prefer not to answer

How difficult is it for you to **do MT-assisted translation**?

- Very easy 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- Very difficult 7
- Not applicable or prefer not to answer

How difficult is it for you to **revise**?

- Very easy 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- Very difficult 7
- Not applicable or prefer not to answer

How difficult is it for you to **translate the traditional way**?

- Very easy 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- Very difficult 7
- Not applicable or prefer not to answer

End of Block: Bloc évolution et appréciation des activités

Start of Block: Profil

You are almost done! We just need some information about you

Which language(s) do you translate **into**?

Which language(s) do you translate **from**?

You are...

- A woman
- A man
- A non-binary person
- I prefer not to answer

For how many years have you been working as a professional translator?

▼ 1 ... 40 years or more

Finally, would you like to make any comments or remarks?

End of Block: Profil
